

counting 200 spores of each treatment. Spores incubated in water and respective solvent in which the compound was dissolved were used as control. Percentage spore germination inhibition was calculated using the standard formula. Similarly, other ketimines (2-5) were tested for their antifungal activity against *Puccinia striiformis*, *Puccinia recondita*, *Alternaria triticina*, *Alternaria tenuis* and *Pestalotia psidii*

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Reaction of Azlactone with Veratraldehyde Schiff Bases

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REACTION of azlactones, which are obtained *in situ* from α -acylamido acids, with carbonyl compounds constitutes a special case of the Perkin reaction. Cinnamalanilines and azlactone of benzoylalanine have been shown to undergo a (4+2)-cycloaddition reaction². In continuation of the work on this reaction with disubstituted benzaldehydes³, this paper describes the reaction of benzoylglycine with veratraldehyde Schiff bases⁴.

A crystalline product, m.p. 162°, was obtained in quantitative yield by the reaction of azlactone, prepared from hippuric acid and acetic anhydride *in situ* in presence of sodium acetate, with 3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde. On the basis of elemental analysis, ir and nmr studies, the compound has been identified as 2-phenyl-4-(3,4-dimethoxybenzal)-5-oxazolone (3). Its spectrum shows absorption bands at 1750 and 1670 cm^{-1} indicative of C=O and C=N linkage, respectively. Nmr spectrum (CDCl_3) of the product indicates 6 methoxy protons at τ 6.0 as a singlet, and a multiplet at τ 2.2-3.4 equivalent to 4 protons thereby showing that olefinic proton merges with the aromatic protons.

It seems, 3 is formed through the electrophilic addition of the enolate, produced by the abstraction of a proton by base from the active methylene part of the azlactone to the Schiff base to give an unstable adduct (2) followed by elimination of amine in the presence of base (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

The product 3 is confirmed by m.m.p. determination (no depression) with authentic sample of 2-phenyl-4-(3,4-dimethoxybenzal)-5-oxazolone synthesised by an unambiguous route¹. Electron-donating substituents (*p*-OEt, *p*-OMe, *p*-Me) in the *N*-phenyl nucleus facilitate the reaction as shown by higher yields of the product, whereas electron-withdrawing groups (Cl, Br) retard it. However, the same product was obtained after amine elimination in all the cases.

Experimental

Reaction of azlactone (1) with 3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde Schiff base: Hippuric acid (1.8 g, 0.01 mol) and 3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (2.41 g, 0.01 mol) were dissolved in dry benzene (50 ml) and to it acetic anhydride (A.R.; 1.2 ml) added. The mixture was heated and allowed to stand at room temperature for 2 days. During this period most of the crude product separated out which was filtered under reduced pressure. The mother liquor on concentration yielded a further crop. The combined crude product

was recrystallised from hot benzene to give light brown crystals of 2-phenyl-4-(3,4-dimethoxybenzal)-5-oxazolone (80%), m.p. 162° (Found: C, 70.02; H, 4.82; N, 4.48. $C_{18}H_{15}NO_4$ calcd. for: C, 69.90; H, 4.85; N, 4.53%).

Reaction with 3,4-dimethoxybenzal-*p*-toluidine, 3,4-dimethoxybenzal-*p*-anisidine, 3,4-dimethoxybenzal-*p*-phenetidine, 3,4-dimethoxybenzal-*p*-chloroaniline and 3,4-dimethoxybenzal-*p*-bromoaniline was carried out by using the above procedure. The above reactions also resulted in formation of 2-phenyl-4-(3,4-dimethoxybenzal)-5-oxazolone (3) (85-70%).

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Synthesis of some New Antifungal Tetrazolyl Sulphides

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A well known fact about 1,2,3,4-tetrazoles is that they have a varied spectrum of biological activities¹. This nucleus when present in a compound imparts anticonvulsant², radio-protective³ and spermatostatic⁴ properties to that compound. The SH group attached to the nucleus may enhance the pharmacological activities⁵. The sulphides have been reported to possess more biological activities than the parent mercapto compounds⁶. Moreover, the heterocyclic disulphides have been known to possess significant antifungal activity⁷. Studies of pesticidal activities of bis(4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)alkanes have indicated that activity increased⁸ with the increase in the number of methylene groups. These studies in the modification of pharmacological activities of heterocyclics, prompted the authors to take up the synthesis of new tetrazolyl sulphides and to screen these compounds for their fungicidal activity. As speculated, these compounds have been found to possess significant fungicidal activity.

1-Aryl-1,2,3,4-tetrazole-5-thiols (3) have been prepared by the method of Freund and Hempel⁹.

These have been converted to bis-tetrazolyl disulphides (4) and to bis-ethylene disulphides (5) according to Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Reagents. (i) HNO_3 ; (ii) aqueous NaOH; (iii) Br_2 ; C_2H_5OH ; (iv) $BrCH_2CH_2Br$; (v) anhydrous CH_3COONa .

The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. Their characterisation has been done by ir spectra. Eighteen of the title compounds have been screened for their fungicidal activity against *A. niger* and *A. flavus*. Some of these compounds exhibited satisfactory antifungal activity.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 521 spectrophotometer. 5-Aryl-amino-1,2,3,4-thiazotriazoles (2) were prepared by the action of HNO_3 on 1 in cold.

Bis(1-aryl-1,2,3,4-tetrazol-5-yl)disulphides (4): The compounds were prepared by oxidation of 1-aryl-1,2,3,4-tetrazole-5-thiol (3) with bromine. To an ethanolic solution (20 ml) of 3 (0.01 M), a cold ethanolic solution (20 ml) of bromine (0.01 M) was added dropwise with stirring. The precipitate thus obtained was filtered, washed with ethanol and recrystallised (Table 1).

Bis(1-aryl-1,2,3,4-tetrazol-5-yl)ethylene disulphides (5): To an ethanolic solution of 3 (0.01 M), anhydrous sodium acetate and ethylene bromide (0.005 M) were added. The contents were refluxed for 4 to 5 h and then poured into cold water. The solid thus obtained was filtered, washed and recrystallised from ethanol (Table 2).

Fungicidal screening: All the nineteen compounds were evaluated for their fungitoxicity by agar plate technique¹⁰ against *A. niger* and *A. flavus* at three different concentrations, namely 1:1 000 and 1:10 000 and 1:100 000. The number of replications in each was three. The percentage inhibition (after 90 h) by various compounds are recorded in Tables 1 and 2.

Results and Discussion

All the tested compounds possessed significant